

First detection of tau neutrinos with KM3NeT/ORCA6

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Abstract

The tau neutrino is one of the least well studied particles in the Standard Model with an overall measured statistics of about 2000 events. KM3NeT/ORCA is a water Cherenkov detector currently under construction in the Mediterranean Sea that aims to determine the neutrino mass ordering. It is optimised for the detection of atmospheric neutrinos in the 1–100 GeV range. While the atmospheric neutrino flux at these energies is initially only composed of electron and muon neutrinos, there is a considerable flux of tau neutrinos at the Earth due to oscillations. KM3NeT/ORCA is sensitive to this flux and can detect tau neutrinos. This contribution highlights the first detection of tau neutrinos with KM3NeT/ORCA6, a preliminary detector configuration.

1 Introduction

Tau neutrinos have first been detected 25 years ago by the DONuT Collaboration [1]. Today, the overall statistics is still low compared to other particles as only few experiments have observed them. Tau neutrinos can be identified via charged-current (CC) interactions $\nu_\tau + X \rightarrow \tau + X'$. The produced tau lepton decays relatively fast into a tau neutrino and an electron, a muon, or hadrons. The two vertices from interaction and decay are characteristic for ν_τ CC interactions but given the tau decay length of $50 \text{ m} \left(\frac{E_{\nu_\tau}}{\text{PeV}} \right)$, these can only be resolved if the detector is densely enough instrumented for a given neutrino energy. The identification of individual ν_τ CC interactions, thus, requires a high resolution, which has so far only been achieved by emulsion detectors [2, 3]. Cherenkov detectors, on the other hand, cannot directly identify individual ν_τ CC interactions, but detect them on a statistical basis.

2 Atmospheric tau appearance with KM3NeT/ORCA

KM3NeT/ORCA is a water Cherenkov detector that is currently built at the bottom of the Mediterranean Sea by the KM3NeT Collaboration [4]. When charged secondary particles from neutrino interactions propagate through the detector or its surroundings at a speed faster than the speed of light in water, they induce the emission of Cherenkov light. This can be captured by the photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) that are arranged on a three-dimensional grid. Thirty one PMTs are distributed almost uniformly in a digital optical module (DOM) inside a pressure-resistant glass sphere [5]. A vertical detection unit (DU) hosts 18 DOMs separated by a distance of 9 m. It is attached to the sea bed by an anchor and held upright by a buoy at the top. The final ORCA detector is foreseen to consist of more than 100 DUs with a distance of 20 m,

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Figure 1: Neutrino oscillation probabilities for $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\tau$ as a function of the true neutrino energy and cosine of the zenith angle. Oscillation parameters from [6], assuming normal ordering.

covering about 7 Mtons of water. Even though the detector is still under construction, it can already take data in preliminary configurations. From January 2020 to November 2021, it was operational in a configuration of six DUs, which is referred to as ORCA6 and corresponds to an exposure of 433 kton-years.

The geometry of KM3NeT/ORCA is optimised for the detection of atmospheric neutrinos at GeV energies to study their oscillations, i.e. measure the atmospheric oscillation parameters Δm_{31}^2 and θ_{23} , and finally determine the neutrino mass ordering. The detection of tau neutrinos is among the primary goals in the early detector phase.

The atmospheric neutrino flux at GeV energies initially consists of electron and muon neutrinos. These are mainly produced in the decay of charged pions and kaons. However, due to neutrino oscillations, mainly $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\tau$, where ν refers to neutrinos and antineutrinos, there is a sizeable flux of tau neutrinos at the detector. The corresponding oscillation probability is illustrated as a function of the neutrino energy and cosine of the zenith angle in figure 1. As can be seen, there is a prominent oscillation maximum with almost full conversion for up-going ($\cos \theta = -1$) particles at 20–30 GeV.

KM3NeT/ORCA cannot identify tau neutrinos on an event-by-event basis. Instead, two event topologies can be distinguished. Track-like events have a muon in the final state, which leads to a characteristic track signature. They are mainly ν_μ CC interactions. Shower-like events are neutral-current (NC) and ν_e CC interactions. In this case, the detector can only observe a hadronic cascade and in case of ν_e CC also an electromagnetic cascade. Depending on the tau decay channel, ν_τ CC interactions can contribute to both topologies but are dominantly ($\sim 83\%$) shower-like.

Consequently, ν_τ appearance can be observed as an excess of shower-like events and measured statistically. This can be quantified by the strength of the tau neutrino signal with respect to the expectation. A measurement has been performed in two scenarios, each of them being motivated by a different scientific goal as described in sections 3.1 and 3.2.

3 Analysis

The measurement of the ν_τ normalisation has been performed with the ORCA6 dataset. The data is classified according to the event topology based on Boosted Decision Trees and is binned in reconstructed energy and direction. The final dataset consists of 5282 neutrino candidates. The model is fitted to the data by minimising a negative log-likelihood $-2 \log \mathcal{L}$. It includes a range of different nuisance parameters, which account for uncertainties in the neutrino oscillation parameters, shape and composition of the atmospheric neutrino flux, detector as well as cross

Figure 2: Left: Observed $-2\Delta \log \mathcal{L}$ profile for S_τ . The uncertainty is derived from the Feldman-Cousins correction, which is given as coloured lines. Right: Measured ν_τ CC cross section.

section modelling. More details about the dataset and the analysis configurations can be found in [7] and [8].

3.1 Measurement of the ν_τ CC cross section

The ν_τ normalisation S_τ is defined as the ratio of expected to detected ν_τ interactions. When applied to CC interactions, it can be interpreted as a measurement of the cross section.

For ORCA6, the ν_τ normalisation was measured to be $S_\tau = 0.48_{-0.33}^{+0.5}$. The corresponding $-2\Delta \log \mathcal{L}$ profile is presented on the left side of figure 2. The coloured lines indicate the confidence levels obtained from the Feldman-Cousins method, which has been used to derive the uncertainty. The best-fit model corresponds to 92_{-63}^{+90} ν_τ CC interactions. Even though the best-fit value is only about half of the nominal value, it is still in agreement with $S_\tau = 1$. The p-value for no- ν_τ appearance, i.e. $S_\tau = 0$, is $(5.9 \pm 0.8)\%$.

The cross section was measured by scaling the expected cross section with S_τ . The theoretical value is taken from GENIE [9] and averaged over the $\nu_\tau/\bar{\nu}_\tau$ ratio in ORCA6. This is indicated as grey dashed line on the right side of figure 2. Finally, it is evaluated at the median energy of the ν_τ distribution of 20.3 GeV. The measured cross section is found to be $\sigma_\tau^{\text{measured}} = (2.5_{-1.8}^{+2.6}) \times 10^{-38} \text{ cm}^2$, which is consistent with the expectation.

3.2 Probing non-unitarity of the neutrino mixing matrix

In a second approach, the ν_τ normalisation is used to probe the unitarity of the neutrino mixing matrix U . As for example shown in [10], non-unitarity can be modelled by the matrix

$$\alpha = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha_{21} & \alpha_{22} & 0 \\ \alpha_{31} & \alpha_{32} & \alpha_{33} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

In this case, the effective non-unitary three-flavour neutrino mixing matrix $N = \alpha \cdot U$ is a sub-matrix of the full $n \times n$ matrix. Considering only α_{33} , while fixing the remaining elements to $\alpha_{ij} = \delta_{ij}$, the tau row of U is scaled by α_{33} . This framework is motivated by the existence of heavy neutral leptons, which do not interact weakly but participate in neutrino oscillations. These require including the neutral-current potential V_{NC} . This can be neglected when only considering active neutrinos, since it is the same for all flavours. Introducing α_{33} and V_{NC} modifies the oscillation probabilities of all channels. If $V_{\text{NC}} = 0$, α_{33} only affects the tau channel. The ν_τ appearance probabilities and consequently the ν_τ rates are scaled by α_{33}^2 . In this sense, α_{33}^2 recovers a CC+NC ν_τ normalisation.

Figure 3: $-2\Delta \log \mathcal{L}$ profile for the measurement of α_{33} with (solid line) and without (dashed line) the inclusion of neutral-current potential V_{NC} .

Figure 4: Comparison of the results by KM3NeT/ORCA6 for S_τ (left) with previous measurements from OPERA [3], Super-Kamiokande [13], and IceCube [11] as well as for α_{33} (right) with a measurement from Super-Kamiokande derived in [14].

The $-2\Delta \log \mathcal{L}$ profile for both cases is presented in figure 3. For $V_{\text{NC}} = 0$, the best fit is found to be $\alpha_{33} = 0.83^{+0.20}_{-0.25}$, and consequently $\alpha_{33}^2 = 0.68^{+0.4}_{-0.35}$. When including $V_{\text{NC}} \neq 0$, $\alpha_{33} = 0.993^{+0.026}_{-0.025}$ and the measurement is significantly more accurate, improving the current limits to $\alpha_{33} > 0.95$ at the 95% confidence level. This limit is more stringent than in the $V_{\text{NC}} = 0$ case as in this case not only the ν_τ appearance channel contributes to the sensitivity. However, in both cases, the measurement is in agreement with unitarity, i.e. $\alpha_{33} = 1$.

4 Summary

KM3NeT/ORCA6 has observed tau neutrinos for the first time. The parameter S_τ was used to determine the ν_τ CC cross section, whereas the non-unitarity parameter α_{33} was used to probe non-unitarity of the neutrino mixing matrix. A comparison of the results from ORCA6 with previous measurements is presented in figure 4.

While the best-fit values for S_τ are distributed between about 0.5 and 1.5, all measurements are consistent with the expectation. In case of α_{33} , the measurement of ORCA6 has improved the current limits. For $V_{\text{NC}} = 0$, the result for α_{33}^2 is in good agreement with the result from [11] and both measurements are consistent with unitarity.

These results were obtained using only about 5% of the final detector but reach already competitive uncertainties compared to previous measurements. As the detector grows, it will collect more data with higher quality. The full detector is expected to measure more than 3000 ν_τ CC interactions per year and constrain the ν_τ normalisation to about 10% [12].

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